

TEACHERS' GENERATIONAL DIVERSITY AND TEACHER'S PROFESSIONALISM

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ABSTRACT

The issue of generational differences in the workplace is one that appears to be impacting all types of organizations in many different parts of the world. Today's workforce is more diverse than ever, and that diversity is creating challenges that expand beyond classroom instruction. This study intention to find out the teachers' generational diversity and teacher's professionalism. This study is a descriptive -correlational kind of research in which it uses a survey questionnaire for easier distribution and collection of data. There were 80 respondents of teachers from the selected elementary schools of San Juan, East District, Division of Batangas, conducted last May 2021. Based on the results, regardless of generation, the use of technology is always practiced and is significantly related to teacher's professionalism in terms of professional training and professional development. However, it is not related to the academic qualification and teaching experience of the respondents. The result also manifests that the teaching methods the respondents applied are based on the level of academic qualification they have and acquired. Interpersonal skill is also found significantly related in terms of professional training and teaching experience. The researcher recommends that the school administrators should provide clear organizational vision considering the strengths and weaknesses of the different generations. It is essential to provide mentoring to all generations both in the field that they excel with and on the areas that they need more rigorous training. Moreover, the administrators and the teachers should accept each generational differences and use them effectively as leverage for the efficient and effective application of technology, teaching methodology, improved interpersonal skills and in maintaining the upright and reputable personality expected on teachers as models of the students, school and the community as a whole

Keywords: Generation, Diversity, Professionalism